

A Table-Oriented Interface for Reliability Modeling of Fault-Tolerant Architectures

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Abstract

This paper describes a spreadsheet interface computer program for capturing the failure characteristics of a fault-tolerant architecture and automatically generating a corresponding reliability model. The level of information required is appropriate for system designers with little or no background in the details of reliability calculations. The system description process and model generation algorithms are presented.

Introduction

The Table-Oriented Translator to the ASSIST Language (TOTAL) computer program is a spreadsheet interface for a reliability analysis tool set under development at NASA Langley. The tool set began with the development of several Markov and semi-Markov model solvers, which provide the flexibility to represent the failure behavior of virtually any fault-tolerant system. These include the Semi-Markov Unreliability Range Evaluator (SURE), the Scaled Taylor Exponential Matrix (STEM) solver, and the Padé Approximation With Scaling (PAWS) program[1, 2, 3]. Since the enumeration of the states and transitions in such a model is intractable for all but the simplest of systems, the ASSIST language was developed to allow the user to describe the failure behavior of the system in a high-level abstract language[4]. The ASSIST computer program was then developed to use the ASSIST description as a set of rules for automatically generating a reliability model[5]. The ASSIST program simply follows the rules as specified by the user and makes no assumptions about the system, so ASSIST is completely general and could theoretically be used to generate a reliability model for virtually any fault-tolerant system. However, the user must learn the concepts and syntax of the ASSIST input language before he can use it, and validation that the ASSIST description is accurate can be difficult for fault-tolerant systems with complex failure properties and dependencies.

The TOTAL interface program allows the user to describe a system at an even higher level of abstraction. Instead of providing the complete flexibility of the ASSIST

language, the TOTAL interface provides the user with a structured set of choices for describing the system components and their interactions. The flow of information between the computer programs in this tool set is shown in Figure 1.

The simplest systems are nonreconfigurable ones whose system failure is based on what combinations of its components have failed. The failure behaviors of these systems can be fully described by listing the components and their failure rates and enumerating which combinations of component failures lead to system failure, such as is done in a fault tree. This description is typically facilitated by grouping like components into subsystems.

Reconfigurable systems can be more difficult to accurately describe. Each subsystem may have spare components that are brought into the active configuration to replace failed components. Once the available spares are exhausted, a subsystem may degrade by removing failed components from the voting process. The system may provide full or partial detection of failed spares. Some spare components may be shared between subsystems and thus available to replace failed components in one or more subsystems.

More complex systems may exhibit failure dependencies between components; for example, failure of a power supply may cause the components dependent upon it to fail as well. A processor may depend on a network element for communication with the other processors in the system. Such dependencies can sometimes be included in the system failure combination descriptions. However, it is often more convenient and concise to list these as separate failure dependencies.

The level of system description given above seems appropriate for designers of fault-tolerant systems, even those with no background knowledge in reliability analysis calculations. This is the level of information needed to build a TOTAL system description. The user does not have to know how to build reliability models; he only needs to know the failure behaviors of his system.

The TOTAL program provides a menu-driven interface to guide the user through each phase of the system de-

Figure 1: Reliability Analysis Tool Set

scription. The system description consists of four parts: 1) a spreadsheet describing the components in the system, 2) specification of the failure dependencies between the components, 3) a description of the conditions representing system failure, and a list of sets of pooled spares that can be shared between the components in the system. As the menu-driven interface guides the user through the system description process, the TOTAL program interactively builds and displays the set of tables describing the system.

Once the system description process is complete, the user can generate the ASSIST-language description, execute the ASSIST program to enumerate the states and transitions of the model, and solve for the probability of system failure using the SURE (or PAWS or STEM) program, all from the TOTAL menu-driven interface.

The following section describes the TOTAL menu-driven interface in detail and illustrates the use of the interface to enter a description of the example system given above. How the TOTAL program derives the ASSIST-language system description is then given. Finally, information on availability of the computer programs is given, followed by some concluding remarks.

System Description using TOTAL

In this section, the TOTAL Menu-Driven Interface will be described and illustrated by way of example. The example system consists of a triplex set of processors with one spare processor, a triplex set of memory units, and a quadruplex bus, as shown in Figure 2. All messages and calculations are subject to majority voting to detect and mask failures. Thus, a majority of the processors in the current configuration must be working, or system failure occurs. Similarly, a majority of the memories and a majority of the buses must be working. Upon detection of the first processor failure, the spare processor is brought into the configuration to replace the faulty processor. Upon the second processor failure, the faulty processor is removed and the remaining two working processors continue in duplex mode. Failure of one of the remaining two processors immediately defeats the majority voter. Each memory unit is attached to one of the processors, and removal of a failed processor also results in removal of its attached memory. The memory units degrade from triplex to duplex to simplex as failed memory units are detected in the configuration or are removed because of processor removals. The bus is nonreconfigurable.

The following subsections will detail how this example system can be described using the TOTAL interface.

Figure 2: Example System

System Description Panel

Upon entering TOTAL, the System Description panel is displayed on the user's workstation. Figure 3 shows the System Description panel containing the description of the example system. This panel contains four tables for displaying the system description:

- Spare Pools
- Components
- Dependencies
- System Failure Conditions.

The Spare Pools table holds the descriptions of any pools of spare components that can be used to replace failed components. The Components table describes the components in the system. Each line of the table represents one subsystem of the system, where a subsystem is made up of like components. Any failure dependencies are depicted in the Dependencies table. Finally, the System Failure Conditions table lists the conditions that are to be modeled as denoting system failure.

Beside each table is an Edit pull-down menu, represented as a rectangle with an arrow pointing down, for entering or modifying entries in that table. Each pull-down menu allows the user to add, delete, or modify entries in the corresponding table. The system description process is guided

System Description (TOTAL V1.0)									
Spare Pools:		poolname	size	failure-rate	prob-of-detection				
[Edit]									
Components:		#	name	redund	trans/int	degrad	dedicated-spare	prob-of-detection	pools:
[Edit]		1	processors	3	trans	3-2-1	1	6.113e-4	Fully
		1	memories	3	trans	3-2-1	0		
		1	bus	4		non	0		
Dependencies:		condition: cause -> effect							
[Edit]		REM(processors[1]) -> REM(memories[1])							
		REM(processors[2]) -> REM(memories[2])							
		REM(processors[3]) -> REM(memories[3])							
System Failure Conditions:		DEATHIF (MAJ(processors))							
[Edit]		DEATHIF (MAJ(memories))							
		DEATHIF (MAJ(bus))							

Figure 3: System Description Panel of Example System

by a set of menus. As the user describes his system using the menus; the system description is displayed in the tables.

Spare Pools

Spare pools are pools of spare components that can be used to replace failed components from multiple subsystems. Consider, for example, a system that contains two triads of processors that share a pool of spare processors. The spare processors would be described in the Spare Pools table and given a name, such as "pspars". The two triads would then be described as two separate subsystems in the Components Table, and each would have "pspars" listed as a source of pooled spares.

Since our example system does not contain any spare components that are shared between more than one subsystem, the system description will not contain any spare pools.

Components

The example system description will contain three entries in the Components table: processors, memories, and

the bus. To input the first entry, the user selects the Append option from the Edit menu beside the Components table. Figure 4 shows the component configuration panel filled in with the correct information to describe the processors subsystem.

Since there is only one set of triplex processors in our example system, the repetition factor is 1. The component name of "processors" is entered. The redundancy count is 3 because there are 3 components in the "processor" subsystem. The user describes how this subsystem degrades when component failures occur by selecting one of the following predefined degradation strategies:

- Non-degradable - No failed components are ever removed from the subsystem.
- Triplex to duplex to simplex - Components are removed from the subsystem one at a time as they fail.
- Triplex to simplex - Components are removed from the subsystem one at a time as they fail until a triplex is reached. Failure of one component of a triplex results in removal of the failed component plus one other component, leaving a simplex.
- Duplex to zero - Components are removed from the subsystem one at a time until a duplex is reached.

On the next component failure, all of the components are removed. This selection is useful for self-checking pairs.

The example “processors” subsystem always degrades by one, so degradation from “triplex to duplex to simplex” is selected. Permanent faults are always modeled, and for this subsystem modeling of transient faults is also selected.

A subsystem can have spares that are dedicated to that subsystem and/or use spares from up to three pools. The user specifies the number of spares dedicated to this subsystem in the Dedicated Spare Count box. Dedicated spares will be substituted for failed components before pooled spares. Dedicated spares cannot be shared across replicated subsystems; they are dedicated to a specific subsystem. Thus, a subsystem specified with a redundancy of 3, a dedicated spare count of 1, and a replication factor of 2 would be a subsystem of two triplexes, with each triplex having one spare dedicated to it.

Since there is one spare processor in the example system, the dedicated spare count is 1. As soon as a nonzero dedicated spare count is chosen, another panel appears for describing the dedicated spares for that subsystem. This panel prompts the user for the failure rate for the dedicated spares. The user must also specify whether the system can detect that spares have failed and remove them from the available spares. This is specified by choosing either:

- Never - The probability of detection that a spare has failed is zero.
- Partially - If this selection is chosen, an additional panel immediately appears for the user to input the probability of detection.
- Fully - The probability of detection that a spare has failed is one; i.e. the system can determine with 100% success that a failed spare is bad and will not use it.

For our example system, the spare is assigned an exponential failure rate of 6.113×10^{-4} , and “Fully” detectability is chosen because it is assumed for this system that failures of the spare are always immediately detected.

The user can specify up to three pools of spares for a subsystem. Any dedicated spares for this subsystem will be used before the Primary Spare Pool. If the name of a Secondary Spare Pool is given, then after the subsystem has used all of its dedicated spares and primary pool spares, then subsequent failed components will be replaced with components from the secondary spare pool. The Tertiary Spare Pool components will be used after all dedicated, primary pool, and secondary pool components are exhausted. The example system contains no pooled spares, so no spare pool names are specified.

After clicking on the “Okay” button, a panel appears for specifying the rates pertinent to this subsystem. The user will only be prompted for the items that pertain to the subsystem specified; for example, the user will be prompted for transient fault arrival and disappearance rates only if he specified that transient faults were to be modeled. Permanent and transient fault-arrival rates are slow exponential

Figure 4: Component configuration for “processors”

rates, and are defined by simply giving a rate in real or exponential notation, such as “1e-4”. The rates for degradation, reconfiguration to bring in a spare, or disappearance of transient faults are fast rates. These fast rates may be given in one of two formats: 1) by giving the mean and standard deviation of the distribution within angle brackets, such as “<3.6e-3,3e-3>”, or 2) by simply giving the rate for an exponentially distributed transition, such as “6.5e5”. If the rate is given, the mean and standard deviation used for this transition will both be equal to the inverse of this rate. After clicking on the “Okay” button on the rates panel, the component specification menus disappear and all changes are reflected in the tables.

The memories and bus subsystems are specified in a similar manner. The memories subsystem description is identical to the components specification, except that the dedicated spare count is set to 0. Since the subsystem has no dedicated spares, the menu for specifying these details does not appear. Since the bus is a nonreconfigurable quadruplex, the redundancy count is 4 and “Non-degradable” is chosen. Transients are not selected since transient faults of the bus will not be modeled. The bus has no dedicated spares.

Dependencies

The Dependencies section allows the user to specify dependencies in the failure behaviors between subsystems in the system. Each dependency has one or more triggering events and one or more effects. A trigger event might be permanent or transient failure of a component, replacement

of a component with a spare, or removal of a component from the active configuration. An effect of a dependency might be the failure or removal of a component, or the incrementing or decrementing of a value in the model. The user can define extra variables to be included in the model and can reference and change their values in dependency effects or system failure descriptions. This can be useful for describing a system with various "modes" of operation.

For example, there is one type of dependency that must be described about the example system. Because the memories are connected to the processors, removal of a faulty processor causes removal of the memory unit attached to it. The dependency between each memory unit and its processor must be specified; removal of processor 1 causes removal of memory 1, removal of processor 2 causes removal of memory 2, and removal of processor 3 causes removal of memory 3.

Dependencies can be either conditional or unconditional. Conditional dependencies are only in effect under certain conditions of the system. For example, if a processor were currently the master of a bus, then failure of that processor would cause failure of the bus. The dependencies in the example system description are unconditional because they are always in effect regardless of the system configuration.

System Failure Conditions

The conditions leading to system failure are defined in terms of functions of the states of the components in the system, for example, majority vote failure of subsystem A or exhaustion of parts in subsystem B. The menu interface presents a list of functions to choose from, or the user may elect to input a textual description. Using this process, the user creates a list of system failure conditions. For the example system, the user would define three system failure conditions: majority vote failure of processors, majority vote failure of memories, and majority vote failure of the bus components. The three conditions are independent in the sense that system failure occurs if any one of the three conditions holds. The TOTAL interface also allows the user to define system failure conditions that are functions of several conditions; for example, system failure occurs if both the primary memory fails a majority vote and the backup memory has failed.

Model Generation using TOTAL

Once the system description process is complete, the user can generate the ASSIST input description for his system and even run the ASSIST and SURE computer programs directly from the menu-driven interface. Several model reduction techniques, such as pruning and trimming, are available through the TOTAL interface[6, 7]. The user can also save the current system description to a file to read back in at a later time.

As shown in the preceding section, the TOTAL menu-driven interface presents the user with a set of choices for describing the characteristics of his systems. The TOTAL

program generates an ASSIST-level description of the system by executing a set of algorithms based on the system description information. The ASSIST language description is made up of the following basic elements: 1) a set of state-space variables, which are used to describe the states of the model; 2) a description of the initial state of the model; 3) a set of transition-description statements that define the legal transitions between states in the model; and 4) a set of system failure conditions for the model; and 5) a set of constants and variable definitions that are used in the transition-description and system failure statements. The basic algorithm used by TOTAL for generating an ASSIST-level description of the system is as follows.

First, the TOTAL program generates the state-space variables, constants, and variable definitions needed to represent the behavior of the components in the system. As an example, the "processors" subsystem of the example system described above is degradable and has a spare that can fail, and both permanent and transient faults can be modeled. Thus, the ASSIST description would need state-space variables to represent the number of working processors in the active configuration, the number that have failed permanently, the number that have failed due to a transient fault, and the number of working and failed dedicated spare processors. Several constants would be defined for the "processors" components; for example, permanent and transient failure and recovery rates.

The next step is to generate transition-description statements to represent the failure behavior for each component in the system. Several transition-description statements are needed to describe each of the component types in the system. For example, the "processors" components can fail permanently or with a transient fault, the transient faults can disappear, failed processors can be replaced with the dedicated spare, and once the dedicated spares are exhausted, the subsystem recovers from failures by degradation. Each of these behaviors is captured in a separate statement. The dependencies must also be included in these statements. For example, the statement that represents removal of processor 1 must also remove memory 1 from the active configuration.

Finally, the system failure conditions for the model are described in the ASSIST language. This simple process consists of replacing each function in the TOTAL description with its underlying formula in ASSIST. For example, the majority vote function name used in TOTAL is replaced with a formula checking whether the number of working processors in the active configuration is greater than the number of failed processors in the active configuration.

As shown in the above description, the process of generating the ASSIST description depends on a set of algorithms for converting the information from the system description tables into an appropriate ASSIST representation. The correctness of this process lies in the generality of the individual algorithms. In other words, the algorithm for generating ASSIST transition-description state-

ments to reflect replacing a failed component with a spare must work correctly for all possible combinations of characteristics that are allowed in the TOTAL system description. It must take into account all possible combinations of dedicated and pooled spares, spare failure rates and detectability, and all possible dependencies that might be involved. This can be especially difficult in the presence of conditional dependencies.

The approach adopted for the development of TOTAL has been to start with a limited set of choices and to carefully analyze the generality of each added feature and its accompanying algorithms. By doing so, we hope to preserve the correctness of the model generation process. We also plan to document the algorithms used so that the user will know exactly what assumptions are in the model and so that the algorithms can be independently checked for accuracy and generalism. Of course, any computer program will contain bugs, so users are cautioned to check the ASSIST model description for reasonableness and accuracy. Also, analysis of the generality of algorithms will grow increasingly difficult as the complexity of the system description choices grows. The example used in this paper was relatively simple, yet the ASSIST file generated by TOTAL was 478 lines long, including comments. As the number of components and the complexity of failure behaviors grows, reliability model descriptions tend to increase combinatorially.

The TOTAL program is significantly limited in terms of the characteristics of systems it can model accurately; however, the user will know when he has reached those limitations because the menu interface will not include those characteristics.

Computer Program Requirements

The TOTAL program was written using the Transportable Applications Environment (TAE) developed at NASA Goddard Space Flight Center. The TAE package was used in order to be portable between different systems and in order to save development time. The program was written in ANSI-standard "C" by David Boerschlein. It currently executes on a VAX under the VMS operating system running DEC-Windows and on a SUN SPARCstation¹ running the Motif windowing system. Future versions may make use of some "C++" code as well. An ANSI-standard "C" compiler, such as is available from the Free Software Foundation ("gcc") or such as is available with the VAX VMS operating system, is required to recompile.

During the development of the TOTAL program, preliminary versions with limited capabilities are being made available to beta-test users in industry, academia, and other government organizations. We have found beta testing to be invaluable in our previous software development projects, not just for debugging the software, but for obtaining valuable feedback and suggestions. Executable versions of the ASSIST and SURE programs will also be made available to TOTAL beta-test sites.

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Concluding Remarks

In the interest of making an early prototype of TOTAL available to beta-test sites, Version 1 of the program has been released with a limited menu-driven interface and no direct input to the displayed tables. Later versions of TOTAL, starting with Version 2.0 will also allow the user to directly input and manipulate data in the tables, and the TOTAL spreadsheet program will maintain consistency between tables. Once Version 2 of TOTAL is released, the novice user will be guided in the system description process by an easy-to-follow menu interface, while the more experienced user will be able to efficiently input data directly into the spreadsheet tables. We plan to continue development of the TOTAL program over the next several years, increasing the capability of the program to facilitate descriptions of more diverse and complex fault-tolerant systems. Possible future enhancements could include graphical fault-tree notation display of system failure conditions and graphical depiction of the system components. Feedback from beta-test sites and in-house use of the program will guide the future development.

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